

THEORETICAL PRINCIPLES FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF STUDENTS' COMMUNICATIVE COMPETENCE BASED ON THE CLUSTER APPROACH

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Abstract.

This article discusses the formation of competence of students in the educational system and its essence, the role and importance of basic competencies in their preparation for educational activities, the formation of skills and qualifications, and the mechanism for the development of their competence. based on pedagogical and technical knowledge, and also highlights issues such as the integrative-differential approach.

Keywords: students, competence, competency, interdisciplinary integration, integrative-differential approach.

The modern labor market today places increasing demands on the quality of education, professional competence and professional training of future teachers, and in turn, competition among graduates of higher educational institutions, including technical universities. If the initial qualification of a specialist requires only suitability for work and the assimilation of narrow information, then competence requires mastery of knowledge not only of a general type, but also of a broad area in particular. The preparation and ability of a specialist to successfully implement his skills implies an increase in the efficiency and quality of his work. The ability to communicate effectively, which today we call communicative competence, has always been of interest to many scientists. In the field of linguistics, sociology, social psychology, pedagogy and other modern fields of knowledge, attention is focused on the theoretical study of interpersonal relationships and human communicative actions. However, the concept of social and communicative competence of an individual, in our opinion, helps to connect socio-humanitarian knowledge with the formation and development of effective communication skills in all life processes of students, and therefore with their practical actions to perform social functions. Accordingly, the importance of scientific recommendations is increasing, which can be taken into account when implementing various educational reforms, in particular, during the transition of the education system to new standards and in the training of future specialists.

According to psychologists, there is another point of view on the structural structure of competence. According to him, there are different competencies in thinking, behavior and attitude, corresponding to the cognitive, behavioral and emotional domains.

Despite all the differences in approaches to professional competence, all authors include communicative competence in their framework.

In the modern period, the professional competence of a specialist also means his communicative competence, that is, the ability to communicate in the conditions of professional activity.

Communicative competence, as defined by Yu. M. Zhukov, is a psychological characteristic of a person as an individual, which manifests itself in communicating with people or in the ability to establish and maintain the necessary relationships with people. Communicative competence includes a set of knowledge, skills and abilities that ensure successful communication processes in a person.

In pedagogical activity, communicative competence is usually understood as the ability to establish and maintain the necessary relationships with students. Competence includes the body of knowledge, skills and abilities that enable effective communication. This type of competence presupposes the ability to change the depth and volume of communication, to understand and be understood by communication partners.

Communicative competence is a developing and predominantly conscious experience of communication between people, formed in conditions of direct interaction. The process of improving communicative competence is associated with personality development. The means of regulating communicative actions are part of human culture, and their acquisition and enrichment occurs according to the same laws as the development and reproduction of the entire cultural heritage. In many ways, the acquisition of communicative experience occurs not only in the process of direct interaction. Communicative competence presupposes adaptability and freedom of use of a person and consists of categories that regulate the system of a person's relations with the social world.

Communicative competence is a person's ability to communicate, knowledge, skills and communicative characteristics that have arisen on the basis of personal and professional experience in the field of information and communication.

The manifestation of communication abilities consists of the following:

- psychological and social diagnostics of the communicative situation necessary for communication;
- programming the communication process in a specific communicative situation;
- implementation of socio-psychological management of communication processes.

Communicative competence has the following forms according to the types of communicative tasks: defining goals, comprehensive assessment of the situation, considering ways of cooperation and communication (interaction), choosing adequate pedagogical strategies, assessing the success of the communication result, being ready to change profession to a similar profession.

The areas of activity of communicative competence determine the possibility of determining its structural components, consisting of motivational-target, cognitive, emotional, behavioral components:

The communicative ability should be considered as personal, holistic, and its implementation by individuals, the structural components of which are cognitive, motivational, emotional and behavioral, determines the effectiveness of a person's communicative activity.

In the studies of Yu. Raven, V.I. Baidenko, N.V. Kuzmin, A.K. Markova, L.I. Berestov and others, the acquisition of professional competencies is conditionally highlighted.

A number of scientists have explored the need to develop professional training of future specialists through the formation of communicative competence in the educational process. In particular, the ability to communicate effectively, which today we call communicative competence, has always been the focus of attention among professionals.

Scientists in our country pay special attention to the development of professional and communication competencies of future specialists.

It is required that students have the necessary level of communicative competence, adapt to the processes of interaction in the educational process, and understand each other when using communication technologies. He explored the scientific and methodological foundations for the formation of pedagogical qualities in the course of future vocational education. Scientists have also conducted significant scientific research on the composition of professional competencies of a vocational education teacher, the importance of communicative competence in future educational activities, and methods for developing competencies.

The professional skill of teacher-teacher Sh.S. Sharipov in the higher education system is determined not only by the body of knowledge and skills, but also by the effectiveness of their application in real educational practice. Competence refers to the ability to use existing knowledge and experience to solve problems in specific situations.

In scientific research U.N. Nishonaliev studied the process of training teachers of labor education in different historical periods and studied an innovative approach to the personality of vocational education teachers.

Theoretical and methodological aspects of training future vocational education teachers are reflected in the research of R. Kh. Dzhuraev.

In the studies of U.I. Noyatov scientifically substantiated the theoretical, organizational and methodological foundations of quality control and education management in vocational educational institutions.

Theoretical and practical aspects of vocational education and the creation of educational literature were studied in the studies of K.T. Limova. These fundamental studies scientifically substantiate the concept of creating educational and methodological literature of a new generation, as well as the process of preparing textbooks for vocational education.

Scientific research aimed at solving the problems of training vocational education teachers based on an integrative approach was studied by the practicing scientist O.A. Abdukusov. The main task in organizing the educational process is the effective use of pedagogical technologies. But until today, most educational technologies are devoted to theoretical problems, and the impact on practice is less noticeable. For this reason, it is necessary to develop methods for more quickly introducing modern pedagogical technologies.

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